

DETAIL C
SCALE 2 : 1

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION		
							Gérard Zinzindhoué Project				
							TITLE: UW-Camera_09-Back				
							DWG NO.				A3
							SCALE:1:1		SHEET 1 OF 1		
DRAWN		NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		MATERIAL:		WEIGHT:	
CHK'D											
APPV'D											
MFG											
Q.A											